
LEVERAGING THE 2026 PROPOSED TAX REFORMS POLICIES ON NIGERIAN ECONOMIC GROWTH: AN EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM NORTH EASTERN STATES OF NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the effects and implications of the 2026 proposed tax reform Bill on Economic growth in Nigeria. By employing a mixed-methods research approach, involving surveys, interviews, and focus groups, this study specifically examine the extent to which Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform affects the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) of Nigeria and further assessed how individual tax reforms will affect Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) of Nigeria. The study adopted a cross sectional survey research design. All Staff of inland revenue service from the three eastern states (Taraba, Gombe & Bauchi) form the population of the study. Primary source of data was employed in this study. Questionnaires was used as the instrument for data collection. A sample size of 384 staff was picked using Bill Godden sample size formula. Proportional stratified random sampling technique was employed in distributing this 384 to the three Boards of inland revenue services in the three north eastern states. The data was tested using percentages, mean, and standard deviation, while the hypotheses was tested using regression analysis and analysis of variance. sequel to the analyses Findings reveals that, Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform have a significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in north eastern states of Nigeria. Equally, individual tax reforms also reveal a significant effect on Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) of Nigeria with particular reference to north eastern states. In line with the findings, the study concluded that the burning issues in the Nigerian tax system are surmountable through proper system of tax reforms. Based on the conclusion, the study recommends that although increasing the VAT rate may sound unpopular in a country ravaged by poverty and hardship, however, a moderate increase has been canvassed by several commentators, would boost government's revenue profile.

Keywords: *Proposed, Tax, Reform, Bill, Economic, Growth, Nigeria,*

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's overdependence on oil revenue makes her a good candidate for tax administration reforms. The urgency of modernizing Nigeria's tax administration (and other fiscal) systems is premised on the realization that the country is rated one of the lowest Tax/GDP ratios in the world. Tax reforms policies become imperative as the government intent on achieving the objective of increasing non-oil revenue by encouraging companies and individuals to pay taxes which will help grow the country's GDP, improve its revenue to debt ratio and enhance its ability to fund budgeted projects and get the economy back on track (Oko & Adie, 2016).

Major tax administration reforms have occurred in a number of developed countries, such as Canada, France, Germany, Japan, Spain, United Kingdom and USA, and developing countries, such as the Eastern European countries, Russia, China, and other economies in transition. In 2000, for example, Germany implemented a tax reform programme that professionalized the tax administration system which resulted in a dramatic advancement in tax collection (OECD, 2019). Equally, the experience of Spain affirms the hypothesis that a more efficient tax administration leads to more revenue generation. Specifically, enforcement, prosecution and tax auditing in Spain yielded an increase in the number of taxpayers from 1.7 million in 1988 to 2.8 million in 1991 (Olsson, Sabbe & Ott, 2024).

However, Nigeria has introduced many tax administration reforms and acts, starting with the Income Tax Management Act (ITMA) of 1961. The most recent one is the Finance Act of 2020 that became effective from January 1, 2021. It contains important changes totalling 20 in number which made a departure from the past. The objectives of the Act among others include ease of doing business in Nigeria for both local and foreign entrepreneurs. Africa is merging market, and Nigeria continues is of Africa. Trade liberalization and expansion of economic activity policies have encouraged inflow of investors into the country from different parts of the globe. The greatest percentages come from China and America. This is followed closed by European and other Eastern countries such as Japan, South Korea, and Asia. With the influx of foreigners and locals into the business arena, it became pertinent to ease the process of doing business in Nigeria. The Finance Act 2020 therefore becomes imperative with the various changes embedded in the document, (Sabbe & Ott, 2024)

Pellechio and Tanzi (2017), opined that an implicit acknowledgement of organizational failure in the tax administration systems of many countries necessitated the need for tax reforms. Thus, for taxation to achieve its desired effect on resource allocation, distribution of income, and macroeconomic stability and growth, tax administration must function effectively and efficiently; tax reforms are warranted for the following reasons: (a) when there is an exigency to modernize tax administration as part of a broad fiscal reform strategy in response to observed deficiency, inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the tax system; (b) as a response to the demands of a growing economy, in which an expansion of the tax net is necessary to incorporate hitherto uncaptured tax payers, for example, the growing number of informal sector players; and (c) when the imperatives of modern information and communications technology (ICT) and applications as well as changes in macroeconomic policies and legislation compel fiscal reforms, for example, to complement economic, trade and investment policies (Silvani & Baer, 2018). The common thread in most countries' tax reform strategies is to enhance tax administration by addressing observed lapses in the tax collection system. This involves simplifying the tax collection/payment process, promoting voluntary taxpayer compliance, and adopting a logical sequence of procedures for efficiently identifying and managing noncompliance. This process should broaden the tax net to ensure that people and businesses outside the existing tax net are brought in, especially those operating in the informal sector of the economy, (Pellechio & Tanzi, 2023). Therefore, in lieu of the above background, the main objective of the study is to examine the effects and implications of the 2026 proposed tax reform Bill on Economic growth in Nigeria by employing a mixed-methods research approach, involving surveys, interviews, and focus groups,

Problem Statement/Justification:

Practically and currently, Nigeria has introduced many tax administration reforms and acts, starting with the Income Tax Management Act (ITMA) of 1961. The most recent one is the Finance Act of 2020 that became effective from January 1, 2021. It contains important changes totalling 20 in number which made a departure from the past. The objectives of the Act among others include ease of doing business in Nigeria for both local and foreign entrepreneurs. Africa is merging market, and Nigeria continues to be part of Africa. Trade liberalization and expansion of economic activity policies have encouraged inflow of investors into the country from different parts of the globe. The greatest percentages come from China and

America. This is followed closed by European and other Eastern countries such as Japan, South Korea, and Asia. With the influx of foreigners and locals into the business arena, it became pertinent to ease the process of doing business in Nigeria. The Finance Act 2020 therefore becomes imperative with the various changes embedded in the document, (Sabbe & Ott, 2024). However, there are certain problem which are likely to occur in the execution of the reform and they include: whether the tax reform Act will be readily assessable to the public; how the Tax Reform Acts are; how effective and efficient is the Nigeria Tax System and the impact the Tax Reform will have on both the public and private sector of the economy. Empirically, in spite of the arguments for or against Nigerian Tax Reforms, only a few researches have been conducted in this area of study. The researchers that have done justice in this area includes Ibe (2017, Okoye and Eze (2018); Olayinka and Faruk (2018); Owulabi and Ogunlalu (2019). Their studies concentrated on the Tax Reforms (proxy by Import Duties Reform, Export Duties Reform, Company Income Tax Reform, Petroleum Profit Tax Reform, Withholding Tax Reform, and PAYE Reform). But however, only few studies focused on the operational variables used in this research study, which are the VAT Reform and CGT Reform. Therefore, it is against these backdrops that this research strives to demystify the effect of Tax Reforms on the Nigerian Economic Growth. This study specifically examines the extent to which Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform affects the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) of Nigeria and further assessed how individual tax reforms will affect Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) of Nigeria.

Therefore, in lieu of the above background, this study seeks to examine the effects and implications of the proposed tax reform Bill on Economic growth in North Eastern states of Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study were to:

- i. Assessed how individual tax reforms will affect Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the extent Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform will affects the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

However, in view of the above research objectives, the following hypotheses are formulated in null form to guide the study.

H₀: Individual tax reforms does not affect Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

Ho: Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform has no significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Conceptual Framework

Under the conceptual underpinning the reviews were done by clearly explaining the variables as depicted in the framework below:

Figure 1: Conceptual Frameworks (developed by the researcher, 2026)

The Concept of Tax Reforms

Tax reform is a process that governments employ to ameliorate the economic, social and political circumstances in a nation. It is an approach for changing the manner that taxes are generated and managed by a public authority. Several works like Aminu and Eluwa (2024) and Oriakhi and Ahuru (2014), have investigated different aspects of tax reforms and how they affect revenue collection in Nigeria. Notably, the Finance Act 2020 was signed on 31st December, 2020 and became effective from January 1, 2021. The Act was introduced to amend the existing Tax and Regulatory Legislation in Nigeria to enhance the ease of doing business throughout the country. The main affected areas are the Capital Gains Act, Company Income Tax Act, Personal Income Act, Value Added Tax, Nigerian Export Processing Zone Act, Oil and Gas Export Free Zone Act, Federal

Inland Revenue Service (Establishment) Act, as well as Customs and Excise Duties Act.(Finance Act, 2020). The main purpose of the new tax laws is to clear some ambiguities that characterize the extant laws and make room for ease of doing business as well as cushioning the effects of the Covid 19 Pandemic. Under the new Act, crisis intervention fund together with unclaimed funds trust were set up to mitigate the impasse of Covid 19 effect. The government is poised to increase production in core agricultural production such as crops, livestock, forestry and fishing hence it separated agricultural business from actual primary production (S. 11.2 CITA).The minimum moratorium was reduced from 18 months to 12 months with respect to tax exemption on commercial banks loans for companies engaging in primary agricultural production and other local businesses. Withholding Tax remains the final tax for these categories of services unlike the previous Act which inadvertently included the provision for management, consultancy, technical, and professional services. S.14 of the CITA was altered to clarify that revenue earned from leasing, containers, non-freight operation or any other incidental income should be subject to tax in accordance with s.9. This provision creates a distinction between revenue from core shipping/freight operations and air activities that should be subject to tax under s.14 of the CITA, and revenue from other incidental activities that should be subject to the general corporate income tax rate of 30%. Finance Act is a significant milestone for Nigeria as it marks a return to an era of active fiscal supervision motivating regular review of the macro environment and stimulation of the economy on an annual or at least regular basis by means of such instruments as a Finance Act. It is instructive that the Finance (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act No.30 of 1999 represents the last time Nigeria utilized this budgetary fiscal tool in moderating the tax environment for business (Wole, 2020).

Personal Income Tax (PIT) Reform

The Cable, (2023) report that, the NTB intends to overhaul the PIT regime of Nigeria by first rearranging its rates and brackets on the levels of income. Further, the NTB intends to encourage distant work and digital nomads through providing that the income earned from employment in Nigeria by persons residing outside Nigeria will be subjected to taxation only if the services are provided physically in Nigeria. It increases the cut-off mark for those whose incomes are low such persons shall be exempted from taxation up to 800,000 naira for one year. The verge below which low tax rates apply was raised to N50 million from the previous limit of 3.2million naira, while a 25% rate would now apply to those with income

above this new threshold. A similar relief is offered small enterprises with only those that earn above N50million per year revenue being obliged to pay tax. The reforms are extended to the structure as well as the application of the withholding tax law. Foreigners buying Nigerian bonds and shares have to pay higher withholding tax rate of 15 percent. Local investors have to pay 5 percent as professional services fee and 2 percent for goods and construction service instead of 10percent paid by foreign and domestic investors previously. Not requiring any legislation, these new rules were put into effect on 1 January by the FIRS. Nigerian residents who make lottery winnings have to pay 5percent tax, while foreigners pay 10%; this regulation replaces the one made in 1997 that excluded them. The only transactions exempted from being subjected to withholding tax are those done “across-the-counter”-where parties should not possess any pre-existing or established contractual relationship, and payment ought to be made immediately, in cash or electronically - and insurance premiums. Also, enterprises having yearly gross sales below 25m naira and those making transactions under 2m naira are not required to pay it.

Value Added Tax Reform

Value Added Tax has been defined by different authors and writers. According to Abata (2019), Value-Added Tax is described as a consumption tax whereby the consumers bear the tax burden. He explained that tax burden is passed from the manufacturer to wholesaler to retailer and finally to the consumer who ultimately bear the burden. VAT is charge on services and goods indirectly therefore, it means that VAT can only be avoided by not buying and consuming the vatable goods or services. Similarly, a vatable person is one who trades in vatable goods and services for survival. This is mainly an indirect tax on services. Olurofimi (2020) argued that, indirect tax imposed on every sale begins at the production and distribution cycle and culminates in sales to the consumers. He went further explained that, consumers absorb VAT as part of sales prices, meaning that VAT is essentially a consumption tax collected throughout the production and distribution system. VAT is broadly based tax on consumption with few exceptions, levied on goods and services at the rate that varies from one country to another.

Okoye and Eze (2018) added that Value Added Tax is a multi-stage tax imposed on the value added to goods and services as they proceed through various stages of production and distribution process and to services as they are rendered with its burden eventually borne by the final consumer and

collected at each stage of production and distribution network. Recently, the Nigerian government raised VAT to 7.5% to fund her 2020 budget. Every call, bank transaction and all services oriented activities in Nigeria, VAT is being charged. Billions of naira is being raised from VAT annually to help fund government programs and policies. VAT has a profound impact on the economic development of the country

Supporting Theory

To establish a theoretical base for this study. This study anchored on the Ability to Pay Theory as its underpinning theory.

Ability to Pay Theory

This theory was propounded by Holmes in 1976. The Ability to Pay theory usually denotes more than mere capacity to pay: those who have more are not only able to, but should pay more. This conforms to a progressive tax system where taxes are paid on a basis of the proportion of those who earn more pay more. So, if Mr A has an income x times greater than Mr B, he or she has an ability to pay that is more than x times greater than Mr B. Ordinarily this is the case with ability to pay theory. The companies that operate in Nigeria do not have the same levels of income; hence they are to pay according to their income and revenue per accounting year. Those companies operating in the oil and gas sector seem to be more financially strong compared to other companies in other sectors.

Prior Empirical Review

Madugba and Joseph (2024) examined the correlation between Value added tax and economic growth in Nigeria. The study covered a 12-year period between 2007 and 2018. Multiple regressions and correlation analysis methods were adopted to analyze data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) within the period under review. The study showed a negative relationship between the value added tax and the gross domestic product which is the measure of economic growth. Further increase in Value Added Tax will have a negative impact on the citizens and by extension the GDP. The study recommended that government should explore other mechanisms to raise funds including blocking linkages and streamlining the structure of government instead of increasing VAT.

Similarly, Olufemi, Jayeola and Naimot (2023) studied the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive and historical research design; secondary data for twenty-four

years (1994 -2017) were collected from various issues of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and annual reports. Tax revenue as an independent variable with dimensions as Value Added Tax (VAT); Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT); and Custom and Excise Duties (CED) while the dependent variable was Economic Growth (EG) measure by the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Analysis was performed on data collected using Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Regression and other post estimations (Jarque-Bera test; Breusch-Godfrey LM and Ramsey Reset Test) to determine the relationship between the variables. The results of the study showed that VAT and CED had a significant relationship with economic growth ($p < 0.05$), while PPT has negative relationship with economic growth ($P < 0.05$). The study concluded that the role of taxation in nation's building is irreplaceable. Taxation remains a strong socio political and economic tool for economic prosperity. It is therefore recommended that government should engage in a complete re-Organization of tax administrative machinery to reduce incidence of tax evasion and avoidance to the barest minimum in order to improve tax revenue and bring more people and establishments into the tax net. Also, tax revenue should be judiciously utilized to provide enabling environment for business survival and economic growth in Nigeria.

Edame and Okoi (2021) examined the impact of tax reforms on investment and economic growth in Nigeria from 2015 to 2019. They used least square method and multiple regression analysis to analyze the data which was obtained from the CBN. The result of the analysis showed that Stamp Duties and Capital Gain Tax have a negative impact on investment and GDP on the side of tax payers but contributes immensely to increase government funds to spend on programmes and policies. The study concluded that taxes reduce amount of money available to tax payers for investment but contributes to government coffers to enable government provide essential goods and services that will turn enhance economic growth and development. The study recommended that the negative impact of tax on the tax payers should be reduce in order to encourage more investment.

Abomaye-Nimenibo, Michael, and Friday (2019) empirically examined the relationship between tax reforms and economic growth in Nigeria. Tax reforms were proxied by CIT, WHT, and CGT while economic growth in Nigeria was proxied by GDP. The study obtained data spanning 2013-2018 from CBN, FIRS, and NBS for the period under review. The authors

adopted quasi-experimental research design and data was analyzed using Chi-Square. The study examines tax revenue and its dimensions of petroleum profit tax and company income tax and economic growth. The study revealed that there is a negative relationship between Capital Gain Tax Reform and Nigerian Economy, but CIT Reform and WHT Reform have positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. The major findings of the study is that without tax revenue the government may not be able to meet her functions of providing securing and maintaining law and order in the country. Therefore, the study recommended that government should make it impossible for companies to evade tax and penalize any company that have registered but evades tax payment.

METHODOLOGICAL RUN DOWN

This study adopted a survey research design using a cross-sectional research method. The area for this research were the North eastern states of Nigeria, Partuclarly, Taraba, Gombe and Bauchi State. The North East region consists of Six (6) States which includes Taraba, Adamawa, Gombe, Bauchi, Borno and Yobe State. The population of the study comprises of all Staff under the employment of the three Boards of internal revenue service in those three selected North eastern states. However, since the population cut across different States, this study employed a proportional stratified random sampling technique to pick the required sample in form of a stratum. Thereafter a sample size of 384 staff was pick using Bill Godden sample size formula. The study has adopted a primary source of data collection. This was achieved via the administration of designed questionnaires to obtain data required for this study. The result of the data generated in this study was presented and analyzed by the use of regression tables under the inferential statistics hence findings was presented, discussed and interpreted, deductive reasoning relevant to the research objective and hypothesis was observed adequately.

Hence finally, the chi-square technique was employed as the technique to test the pre-set hypothesis which was intended to guide the study.

NOTE: Chi-square (X^2) Formula is depicted as follows:

$$X^2 = \frac{FO - FE}{FE}$$

Where:

FO=frequency Observed

FE=frequency Expected

X²= chi-square

Reject HO if X^2 Calculated is greater than X^2 Tabulated and Vice-versa.

4DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSES AND INTERPRETATIONS

Questionnaire Administration

In this research study, a total number of two hundred and eleven (211) questionnaires that consisted of the sample size were prepared and administered to the respondents in the case study. In the course of the distribution and retrieval of the 211 questionnaires (that represents 100% of the total responses) from the sample respondents, a total number of 41 questionnaires that consisted of 19.43% of the total responses were returned wrongly filled, while 98 questionnaires that consisted 46.44% of the total responses were not returned to the researcher, however it was the remaining 72 Copies of questionnaires representing 34.12% of the respondents responses that were successfully filed and retrieved by the researcher. Therefore, this 72 successfully filled and retrieved questionnaires will be the adequate questionnaires that will be used in this study for the purpose of analysis, generalizations as well as conclusions. Hence the questionnaire distribution and retrieval analysis can be shown in the below table as follows:

Table 4.1: Response Rates Statistics Table

Details	number	percentage%
Copies Retrieved and Filed	72	34.12
Copies wrongly Filed	41	19.43
Copies Not Returned.	98	46.44
TOTAL Copies Sent Out	72	100

Source: Researcher survey may 2026

Test of Hypothesis One.

Ho: Individual tax reforms does not affect Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

TABLE 4.2: Chi -square contingency table for Hypothesis one

	FO	FE	FO - FE	(FO - FE ²)	(FO - FE ² /FE)
Q1	9	8.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0031
	8	8.75	-0.5	0.25	0.0325
	6	5.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0308
	6	5.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0108
Q2	13	8.75	4.25	18.0625	2.0642
	7	8.75	- 1.75	3.0625	0.35
	6	5.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0108
	3	5.75	2.75	7.5625	0.0108
Q3	6	8.75	-2.75	7.5625	0.8642
	11	8.75	2.25	5.0625	0.5785
	5	5.75	-0.75	0.5625	0.0978
	7	5.75	1.25	1.5625	0.2717
Q4	7	8.75	-1.75	3.0625	0.35
	9	8.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0071
	6	5.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0108
	7	5.75	1.25	1.1625	0.3717
TOTAL				Calculated value	5.7732

Source: Researcher Computation February, 2026

Chi - square critical table value at 5 under 7 using the X² Table= **2.036**

DECISION RULE:

Since the Chi square-calculated value (**5.7732**) is greater than the chi square-critical table value (**2.036**) at an infinite degree of freedom and 0.05 percent level of significance, therefore we reject the Null hypothesis **H0** which state that, Individual tax reforms does not affect Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria and accept the Alternative hypothesis **H1** to conclude that, Individual tax reforms has significant effect on Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis two

Ho: Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform has no significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

TABLE 4.3: Chi -Square Contingency table for Hypothesis two

Q	FO	FE	FO-FE	(FO-FE) ²	$\frac{(FO-FE)^2}{FE}$
5	11	10.25	0.75	0.5625	0.0343
	5	7.75	-2.75	7.5625	0.6748
	6	5.25	0.75	0.5625	0.3071
	7	5.75	1.25	1.5625	0.2717
6	8	10.25	-2.25	5.0625	0.4939
	12	7.75	4.25	18.0625	2.3306
	4	5.25	-0.75	1.5625	0.2976
	5	5.75	-3.25	10.5625	1.00978
7	7	10.25	3.25	10.5625	1.0304
	11	7.75	3.75	14.0625	1.3529
	6	5.25	3.75	14.0625	2.6785
	5	5.75	-0.75	0.5625	0.0978
8	15	10.25	4.75	22.5625	2.2012
	3	7.75	-4.75	22.5625	2.91129
	5	5.25	-0.25	0.0625	0.03190
	6	5.75	0.25	0.0625	0.0408
			Calculated Value		12.233

Source: Researcher Computation February, 2026

Calculated Value= 12.233

Critical table value at 14 under 9 using the X² Table value= **5.390**

DECISION RULE.

Since the Chi square-calculated value (**12.233**) is greater than the chi square-critical table value

(5.390) at an infinite degree of freedom and 0.05 percent level of significance, therefore we reject the Null hypothesis **H₀** which state that “Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform has no significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria and accept the Alternative hypothesis **H₁** to conclude that, Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform has significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria.

Discussion of Major Findings

Sequel to the analyses the major findings arrived at in this study can be summarized as follows:

- i. Individual tax reforms have significant effect on Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria
- ii. Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform has significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria

However, this finding is in line with the work of (Abolarinwa, 2018). but contradicts the study result of (Wachira, 2013)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

In line with the findings this study concluded as follows:

- i. Individual tax reforms have significant effect on Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria
- ii. Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform has significant effect on the Real Gross Domestic (RGDP) in North Eastern States of Nigeria

However, in line with the findings and the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Government should ensure the conduct of regular audits, and put in place independent anti-corruption measures and properly-defined service delivery machinery.
- ii. The discrepancy between **NTB** and **NTAB** with respect to who should impose VAT or submit monthly returns to the Service should be resolved before the bill are signed into law.
- iii. An improved tax reform that has well-regulated relief allowance and differentiated rates of VAT is likely to assist in increasing equity and redistribution ability of tax system in Nigeria (Edeh, 2021).

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